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The Impact of Central Bank Policy, Green Bond Issuance, and Environmental Concerns on Green Investment Infrastructure in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine how financial support for environmentally friendly projects and the overall economic welfare of a country can influence investments in environmentally sustainable initiatives. By analyzing the objectives of new classical economics and the triple bottom line approach, the study explores the impact of central bank decisions and the issuance of special economic instruments for green projects. Using data from Pakistan spanning from 1997 to 2022, the study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) statistical approach to assess both short-term and long-term effects. The findings indicate that while green bond issuance negatively affects green investment infrastructure in both the short and long term, sustainable economic growth and environmental performance lead to an increase in such investments within a country. Despite the negative impact of green bond issuance on such infrastructure, the findings underscore the positive influence of sustainable economic growth and environmental performance.

Keywords: Green investment; Central bank policy; Green bond issuance; Environmental Concerns; ARDL approach; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of economics and environmental consciousness, the role of monetary policy has gained new significance in addressing the challenges of climate change and sustainability. However, most central banks have yet to consider their role in assisting society in achieving its environmental objectives and understanding the potential implications of environmental degradation for their mandates. Under goal 8, the integration of monetary policy into the broader discussion on sustainable development recognizes the importance of aligning financial and economic systems with social considerations (Bashir et al., 2024). A green economy is crucial to counter the effects of emerging challenges like environmental degradation, climate change, and the transition to renewable energy, which have the potential to destabilize ecosystems and a country's economy. While the Paris Agreement primarily focuses on national-level commitments, monetary policy in Pakistan plays a significant role in promoting green investment and has substantial implications for financial stability, green bonds, and climate funds (Qing et al., 2024). Monetary authorities can collaborate with government agencies, international organizations, and financial institutions to advocate for green investment, including participating in global climate finance initiatives and promoting policies aligned with the Paris Agreement.

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Pakistan's monetary policy can play a vital role in supporting the country's commitments under the agreement by aligning with financial risks and promoting environmentally responsible and stable economic growth (Saqib et al., 2024). Green banking is an emerging concept in Pakistan's economy, aiming to assess individuals' perceptions and responses to green practices adopted by banks. The economic output of solar energy development has become a primary concern, particularly in emerging nations like Pakistan, with a focus on sustainable green revolution through improved solar energy projects. The moderating role of top management and risk factors between financial management procedures and the economic output of solar energy projects is also significant. Pakistan's economy should foster a green industrial revolution to mitigate pollution and increase environmental sustainability, connected with lower carbon emissions but requiring technical innovation, research and development investment, and inbound FDI (Mehmood et al., 2024). Additionally, green finance aims to ensure economic progress while safeguarding the environment and maintaining environmental integrity. The green financing landscape in Pakistan is evolving, necessitating a comprehensive gap analysis to examine the present status and constraints in supporting green finance. Many banks in Pakistan demonstrate a strong commitment to expanding the State Bank of Pakistan's Green Banking Guidelines, highlighting the high value of government assistance for businesses participating in green initiatives and incentives for banking institutions and private limited companies to support and invest in green practices (Ahmed & Jafri, 2024).

Environmental degradation has become a major concern for the international community, leading policymakers to shift their focus from traditional economic growth to sustainable growth known as green growth. Pakistan is currently following a path of weak sustainability, requiring a shift towards strong sustainability to restrain increasing natural resource depletion. As the fifth most vulnerable country to environmental hazards, Pakistan's path to green growth not only protects the environment and human beings but also serves as a substitute for scarce natural assets. Institutions play a vital role in developing laws and policies for all industries, directly responsible for natural resource exploration and environmental protection or destruction (Khan et al., 2024). A survey among central banks in the Asia-Pacific region reveals a consensus on the key role they should play in promoting green finance and sustainable funding options. Environmental factors such as increased energy demand, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, and decreased fossil fuel subsidies are associated with greater green bond issuance. Monetary policy has the potential to ensure an inclusive clean environment in developing countries, where the lack of a clean environment exacerbates poverty and income inequality (Saad-Filho & Feil, 2024). Green credit policies, Sharia compliance, diversification, liquidity ratios, and nonperforming loans also affect the financial performance of banks in Pakistan. Green energy and eco-innovations have the potential to improve air quality and contribute to economic growth by reducing CO₂ emissions. Investment in green innovation reduces environmental deterioration among the world's greenest nations, promoting green investment and implementing environmentally friendly policies (Manigandan et al., 2024).

The research questions and objectives aim to explore specific tools and mechanisms used by central banks to incentivize or support green financing and investment, analyze the impact of increased green investment on GDP growth, and assess how central banks balance traditional mandates with sustainability goals. The significance of this study lies in the pivotal role monetary policy plays in promoting green investment and sustainability, providing financial support for renewable energy and environmentally friendly technologies, boosting market confidence, and fostering economic stability and sustainable growth. However, challenges such as Pakistan's economic growth issues, the role of the State Bank of Pakistan, and international agreements like the Paris Agreement must be addressed to achieve better economic policies and sustainable green economic conditions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review is divided into two parts. The first part discusses the impact of independent variables such as access to sustainable economic growth, environmental performance, and central bank policy on the dependent variable of green investment. In the second part, we will delve into the impact of two independent variables: green bond issuance and credit availability on the dependent variable of green investment. Chen et al. (2023) explore the environmental transformation of traditional sectors and the establishment of new pro-ecological businesses through green investment as the main driving forces. Their objective is to investigate the impact of green investment and technological progress on green industrial development. The study indicates a positive relationship between green finance investment and the industrial structure, emphasizing the need to increase green investment and technological development at a top-level design. Similarly, Shah et al. (2023) address the decline in energy efficiency and productivity in South Asia (SA) over time. They identify potential causes such as inefficiencies in the energy conversion process, extensive input utilization, and limited output growth. The study investigates the role of energy efficiency and productivity growth in the ecological improvement of South Asia, emphasizing the detrimental effects of extensive energy consumption on greenhouse emissions, environmental degradation, and energy efficiency. Hung (2023) analyzes sustainability in Vietnam, highlighting opportunities represented by green investment, digitalization, and financial development. The study demonstrates a strong positive effect of digitalization, green investment, and financial development on economic sustainability in Vietnam, indicating that investment in green resources, technology innovation, and financial development supports the country's transition to sustainable development. Hunjra et al. (2023) investigate the impact of green finance and environmental degradation on sustainable development in developing countries. They use adjusted net savings to measure sustainable development, with green credit, green securities, and green investments serving as proxies for green finance. The analysis reveals a positive and

significant impact of green finance on sustainable development, while environmental degradation exerts a negative and significant impact, suggesting implications for policymakers aiming to achieve sustainable development in developing countries. Similarly, Jahanger et al. (2023) analyze the role of green finance and clean energy in reducing carbon emissions, along with economic growth, foreign direct investment, and urbanization as control antecedents. They propose strong financial mechanisms and long-term green investment strategies to attract green finance and investment opportunities to bridge the gap in clean energy.

Furthermore, Amin (2022) provides a detailed qualitative assessment of demographic, social, and technological factors favorable for the growth of Fintech in Pakistan, highlighting the role of sound regulations by the Fintech regulatory body to aid in the penetration of Fintech. Dikao & Volz (2021) analyze how climate risks can directly affect central banks' traditional core responsibilities. They emphasize the importance of addressing climate-related risks and supporting mitigation and adaptation policies within central bank mandates. The study suggests incorporating climate-related risks into policy frameworks to safeguard macro-financial stability. Desalegn et al. (2022) incorporated inward and outward foreign direct investment, as well as greenhouse gas levels, as control variables in their study. They found that monetary policy, as measured by interest rates and the broad money supply, has a mixed effect on the level of green financing. While interest rates show a negative relationship with green finance, outward foreign direct investment and greenhouse gas levels also display a negative and significant relationship. The study suggests various green finance and green monetary policy approaches, providing implications for key stakeholders in green financing. It advises central banks, credit institutions, and regulatory authorities to consider both neoliberal and reformist approaches to green finance and green monetary policies to foster increased green investment. Orazio & Popoyan (2019) addressed these issues by proposing a critical review of existing and novel prudential approaches to incentivizing the decarbonization of banks' balance sheets and aligning finance with sustainable growth and development objectives. Their analysis helped understand under which conditions macroprudential policy could tackle climate change and promote green lending while containing climate-related financial risks. Although the role of central banks and financial regulators in supporting a smooth transition to a low-carbon economy is recognized, information on which macroprudential instruments could be used for reaching the "green structural change" remains limited. Taran et al. (2020) explored factors affecting green investment awareness, access to green capital, the role of the Government, and green capital mobilization tools, which substantially impact the implementation of green investment by Vietnamese businesses. Their survey included various factors such as infrastructure for green investment, difficulties in accessing funding for green investment activities, incentives for accessing capital for green investment, and understanding of enterprises' green investment. The study suggests raising awareness among businesses about accessing and using these capital-raising tools and promoting green investment communication to address the challenges identified through the evaluation of more than 200 surveyed enterprises. Lyeonov et al. (2019) examined the linkages between GDP per capita, greenhouse gas emissions, renewable energy in total final energy consumption, and green investments, measured as private investments, jobs, and gross value added related to circular economy sectors. Their findings indicated a correlation between these factors, with green investment potentially contributing to the growth of GDP per capita, the decline of greenhouse gas emissions, and the increase of renewable energy consumption.

Pimonenko et al. (2019) aimed to explore green investments as an alternative means to finance the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Their analysis demonstrated the snowballing effect of the green finance market development globally. The study highlighted the correlation between a country's commitment to international climate-related expenditure, the volume of climate finance, and its rating on the Sustainable Development Index. Countries with higher volumes of green investments tended to achieve higher positions on the Sustainable Development Index. Plane Balcilar et al. (2023) focused on the impact of green energy consumption and investment on economic growth, particularly in the context of global warming and significant climatic changes. Their findings indicated that while renewable energy consumption and expenditure in renewable energy research and development have small positive effects on economic growth, capacity utilization in green energy consumption and investment has not yet reached a viable level to mitigate greenhouse effects and spur sustainable development. Chen & Ma (2021) examined how financial performance has been significantly improved through environmental tax, government subsidies, and technological innovation, all of which have positive moderating effects on green investment. Their findings suggest that green investment helps reduce environmental violations and promote environmental performance, ultimately improving the long-term performance of firms. Cheng et al. (2023) investigated the impact of ESG disclosure scores and brand reputation on the issuance of green bonds. They found significant positive effects of ESG disclosure scores and their interaction with brand reputation on green bond issuance. This suggests that firms may need superior corporate social responsibility performance, represented by high ESG scores, in addition to brand reputation to successfully issue green bonds. The study has managerial implications for analysts, fund managers, and firms planning to raise green capital. Ning et al. (2023) focused on the role of green bond financing in energy efficiency investment and economic growth. They highlighted that bank loans are currently the primary source of financing for energy efficiency projects, but green banks invest both public and private funds in energy efficiency, thereby promoting economic growth. The study suggests that

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green bonds have vast potential for financing environmentally beneficial projects and removing financing barriers for green finance and sustainability tools. Rodriguez et al. (2023) analyzed the financing of green innovations and emphasized the need for more policy instruments, especially at the small and medium enterprise level, to further boost the green bond market. Their analysis provides valuable insights for market participants, researchers, policymakers, and decision-makers. Nguyen et al. (2023) explored the development status of green bonds in Southeast Asian countries, aiming to extend knowledge and provide implications for practitioners and policymakers regarding the development of green bonds in the region.

Tang et al. (2023) investigated the relationship between green investments and the climate crisis, particularly in the context of green bonds. They concluded that uncertainties should be considered when investing in green bonds and managing investment portfolios. Lin & Su (2023) examined the determinants of green bonds in the US and China, highlighting financial and economic policy uncertainties as influential factors. They discussed the investment implications and policy significance of their findings. Mirza et al. (2023) studied the positive relationship between green SME lending and net interest margin, suggesting financial incentives for banks to extend sustainable credit to SMEs. They emphasized the potential contribution of commercial banks to sustainability goals through sustainable lending practices. Zhang et al. (2023) verified the effectiveness of a proposed credit evaluation model for SMEs using deep learning techniques, aiming to improve their competitiveness and financing accessibility under economic globalization. Zhao et al. (2023) explored the impact of credit allocation policies on green development by reducing credit allocations to heavily polluting enterprises. They found that investment-cash flow sensitivity increased significantly for these enterprises after the implementation of the policy. Neef & Ongena (2023) compared the issuance of "green loans" and "sustainable loans" to firms based on ESG criteria. They found that sustainable loans incentivize firms to improve their ESG performance, suggesting that the issuance of sustainable loans may lead to subsequent improvements in a firm's overall ESG performance.

It is evident that Pakistan's economic landscape presents both challenges and opportunities in addressing environmental objectives. Central to this discussion is the role of monetary policy, which requires a deeper examination in terms of its alignment with environmental goals, particularly in the context of climate change and sustainability challenges. Moreover, there is a pressing need to establish regulatory frameworks that incentivize green investments and facilitate the transition towards a more sustainable economy. The research underscores the importance of incorporating green finance practices within the banking sector to encourage environmentally friendly behavior among employees and to promote the adoption of sustainable practices throughout the industry.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.1. *New Classical Theory*

The new classical theory encompasses a set of ideas concerning how economies operate, emphasizing both financial management and environmental sustainability. Particularly relevant in developing economies, this theory addresses economic challenges while advocating for effective monetary management to support eco-friendly projects, thereby contributing to the fight against climate change (Azam et al., 2023). Within this framework, decision-makers' behavior is significantly influenced by cooperation levels, although government alignment with central bank goals surprisingly does not disrupt the balance between budget deficits and interest rates within economic equilibrium (Stawska & Malaczewski, 2023).

3.2. *Green Keynesianism Theory*

Green Keynesianism advocates for an economy that prioritizes environmental preservation. Supporters of the Green New Deal envision a cycle wherein increased investment leads to job creation, higher incomes, and overall economic growth, aligning with Keynesian principles and linking environmental objectives with economic prosperity (Green, 2022). However, challenges arise, as factors such as excessive shareholder payouts, inadequate capital spending, and investment uncertainty can impede the success of central bank interventions aimed at promoting green policies (Sanagavarapu, 2022). While green government bonds signal environmental concerns, doubts linger about their effectiveness in driving the green transition and stimulating economic growth simultaneously (Witkowsky, 2022).

3.3. *Triple Bottom Line Theory*

The Triple Bottom Line approach considers economic, social, and environmental factors to achieve balanced and sustainable outcomes for people, planet, and profit. In the context of green credit policy, efforts involve regulating external financing to influence economic growth positively (Wu et al., 2022). Green bonds have emerged as a financial tool aligned with Triple Bottom Line principles, encouraging businesses, investors, and governments to adopt holistic and sustainable approaches to finance and development (Russo & Mariani, 2021). Collateralizing green bonds in central bank lending programs and enhancing issuance advantages not only align with this theory but also contribute to a more sustainable financial system (Fang et al., 2023). By considering economic, environmental, and social dimensions, the Triple Bottom Line approach promotes holistic governance and sustainable economic development, fostering long-term value for companies and stakeholders (Ashta, 2021; Jr. & Gabriel, 2018).

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The dataset for this study, focusing on understanding the impact of monetary policy on promoting green financing and sustainable economic growth, includes various variables sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI, 2023) database for the time period spanning 1997 to 2022. To prepare the data for analysis, natural logarithm transformations are applied across all variables within the dataset to ensure consistency and facilitate statistical analysis. The independent variables selected for this research theme are as follows:

- I. Central Bank Policy (CBP): This variable represents the interest rate, expressed as a percentage. It serves as a key indicator of the monetary policy stance adopted by the central bank.
- II. Green Bond Issuance (BOND): Proxied by market capitalization as a percentage of GDP, this variable measures the extent of green bond issuance in the economy. Green bonds are financial instruments designed to fund environmentally sustainable projects.
- III. GDP per Capita in Constant 2015 US\$: This variable serves as a proxy for Sustainable Economic Growth (SEG) and represents the gross domestic product per capita adjusted for inflation and expressed in constant 2015 US dollars. It reflects the economic performance and standard of living in the country over time.
- IV. Environmental Performance (ENVP): This variable is measured by CO2 emissions in metric tons per capita. It serves as an indicator of the environmental performance of the economy, specifically in terms of greenhouse gas emissions per capita.

By analyzing the relationships among these variables, the study aims to gain insights into how central bank policies influence green financing initiatives and contribute to sustainable economic growth. The empirical estimation process of the study involved the following steps:

Step 1: Unit Root Test

The unit root test was conducted to assess the stability of the economic indicators over time. This test helps economists determine whether the variables exhibit random fluctuations or follow a predictable pattern, aiding in better understanding and prediction of economic trends. Both the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PPT) tests were employed. These tests evaluate whether a time series variable possesses a unit root, indicating whether it tends to remain at a constant level or exhibits a trend. The PPT test, similar to ADF, adjusts for potential autocorrelation in the data.

Step 2: ARDL Modeling

The study utilized the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to formulate equations and comprehend the short-term and long-term effects within a dynamic system. This modeling approach considers how a variable is influenced by its past values (auto-regression) and the impact of past values of another variable on the current one (distributed lag). The ARDL model is particularly valuable for analyzing the dynamics of economic and time-series data. In this context, the ARDL model examined the relationship between equity prices and macroeconomic variables such as inflation, industrial production, oil prices, short-term interest rates, exchange rates, foreign portfolio investment, and money supply. The bounds testing procedure proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001) was employed for this analysis.

Step 3: ARDL Bound Testing Approach

The ARDL bound testing approach was utilized to test the null hypothesis (H_0) of no cointegration against the alternative hypothesis (H_1) of cointegration. This approach helps determine whether there exists a long-run relationship between the variables under investigation. By conducting bound tests, the study assessed the presence of cointegration among the variables, which is crucial for understanding their long-term associations and dynamics.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the unit root estimates for ready reference. The results of the analysis indicate that, with the exception of the variables ENVP (Environmental Performance) and CBP (Central Bank Policy), all other variables are level stationary. Level stationary means that these variables do not exhibit significant trends or patterns over time and tend to fluctuate around a constant mean. On the other hand, ENVP and CBP are first-differenced stationary, which means that their first differences (changes from one period to the next) are stationary.

Table 1: ADF Unit Root Estimates

Variables	Level (Intercept/trend and intercept)		First difference (Intercept/trend and intercept)	
GREEN	-0.594826 (0.865)	-3.422600 (0.0544)	-2.766744 (0.0670)	-2.751778 (0.2189)
BOND	-3.091764 (0.0307)	-3.221292 (0.0868)	-2.179923 (0.2150)	-2.244629 (0.4593)
SEG	0.036239 (0.9590)	-3.221977 (0.0862)	-2.827783 (0.0580)	-2.877782 (0.1742)

ENVP	-1.681833 (0.4373)	-3.024436 (0.1309)	-3.447836 (0.0115)	-3.426404 (0.0537)
CBP	-2.549226 (0.1072)	-3.056554 (0.1227)	-3.252803 (0.0199)	-3.257160 (0.0796)

Source: Author's estimate. Small bracket shows probability value.

This suggests that these two variables display trends or patterns over time that can be accounted for by examining their changes rather than their absolute values. Overall, understanding the stationarity properties of these variables is crucial for accurately modeling their relationships and dynamics in the context of the study. Table 2 presents the criteria used for selecting the lag length in the ARDL regression model. The analysis determined that the optimal lag length for the model is 2, indicating that including two lagged values of the variables provides the best balance between model complexity and explanatory power. This lag length selection is essential for capturing both short-term and long-term effects in the dynamic relationship between the variables under study. With lag length 2 identified as optimal, the ARDL regression model can effectively capture the temporal dynamics and interactions among the variables, enhancing the accuracy of the empirical estimates and ensuring robustness in the analysis.

Table 2: Lag length Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-183.5761	NA	2.01e-06	3.908786	4.068047	3.973184
1	882.7682	1978.783	1.19e-15	-17.33543	-16.22060	-16.88465
2	1104.795	384.5419*	2.60e-17*	-21.17104*	-19.10065*	-20.33388*
3	1114.066	14.90883	4.61e-17	-20.61991	-17.59396	-19.39636
4	1130.779	24.81139	7.14e-17	-20.22224	-16.24073	-18.61232

Source: Author's estimate. Note: * indicates optimal lag length.

Table 3 shows the ARDL estimates and found that green bond issuance has a negative impact on green investment infrastructure both in the short and long run. Conversely, sustainable economic growth and environmental performance have a positive effect on green investment infrastructure, leading to an increase over time. These findings suggest that while the issuance of green bonds may not directly contribute to enhancing green investment infrastructure, factors related to sustainable economic growth and environmental performance play a significant role in driving investments towards eco-friendly projects and initiatives.

Table 3: ARDL Short Run And Long Run Estimates

Short-Run Estimates				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-Statistic	Prob.
D(GREEN(-1))	0.694373	0.062872	11.04417	0.0000
D(BOND)	-0.007697	0.001414	-5.445125	0.0000
D(BOND(-1))	0.006796	0.001377	4.936288	0.0000
D(SEG)	1.752222	0.880695	1.989590	0.0498
D(SEG(-1))	-2.079807	0.919535	-2.261804	0.0262
D(ENVP)	-0.343973	0.273976	-1.255487	0.2127
CointEq(-1)	-0.146027	0.024869	-5.871860	0.0000
Long-Run Estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-Statistic	Prob.
BOND	-0.011158	0.003250	-3.432913	0.0009
SEG	3.593331	0.445109	8.072918	0.0000
CREDIT	-0.158827	0.286487	-0.554396	0.5807
ENVP	1.353204	0.541195	2.500399	0.0143
CBP	0.005302	0.008908	0.595199	0.5533
C	-18.66717	2.963865	-6.298254	0.0000

Source: Author's estimate.

The findings of Rahim & Muzaffar (2024) suggest that financial development affects both the short and long run. Their cointegration estimations reveal a stable, long-term, and significant relationship among the variables under consideration. Pakistan, *Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory*, 2(1), 121-131 (2023)

being vulnerable to global warming, serves as an essential case study for researchers. Chandio et al. (2024) found that climatological elements such as temperature and CO₂ emissions have a detrimental impact on apples output, whereas precipitation has a favorable impact on both in the long and short run. This underscores the importance of formulating appropriate policies to mitigate the negative impacts of global warming on the fruits industry, ensuring sustainable food production to meet domestic and international trade goals. Awan & Yaqoob (2023) underscores the urgent need for R&D development and the adoption of the latest technologies to facilitate rapid GDP growth and expansion. Saleem et al. (2023) found that the effects of exports on economic growth are asymmetric. Notably, economic growth in Pakistan reacts positively to both the rise and fall of exports. Khan et al. (2023) found that an increase in the money supply by the central bank lowers the demand for loans and thereby reduces the cost of loans. Additionally, financial sector development decreases the lending rate, lowering the cost of loans further. Roussel et al. (2021) suggest that financial development and investment exert a positive impact on economic growth both in the long and short run. They also observed a positive relationship between the real deposit rate and economic growth in the long run. Iqbal et al. (2023) found that positive changes in GDP, CO₂, and financial development lead to a significant increase in renewable energy production in the long run. However, negative changes in these variables had no significant impact on renewable energy production in the long run. Ali et al. (2023) suggested a balanced monetary policy to tackle food inflation effectively. Zahid et al. (2023) found that monetary uncertainty negatively affects the economy, while factors like exchange rate, interest rate, and inflation positively influence economic growth in the long run. Rafay et al. (2023) showed that development in the banking sector and gross domestic product positively influence the development of the capital market, while inflation, trade openness, and foreign direct investment have negative effects. Humayun et al. (2023) found that Pakistan's sustainability is endangered by mounting energy use and an unsustainable energy framework primarily dependent on coal.

Table 4 indicates that according to the ARDL Bounds test, the value of the F-statistic falls within the upper bound value. Therefore, it is inferred that the variables are cointegrated in the long run.

Table 4: ARDL Bound Estimates

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	4.604304	4
Significance	I(0) Bound	I(1) Bound
10%	2.08	3.01
5%	2.39	3.38
2.5%	2.7	3.73

Source: Author's estimate.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to elucidate how managing finances for green projects affects economic growth and influences investments in environmentally friendly initiatives. The primary objective was to identify the driving factors behind financial decisions and their connection to supporting green projects, ultimately impacting the success of green investments. Utilizing data from Pakistan spanning from 1997 to 2022, the study focuses on analyzing the financial choices that promote a green economy. There is a significant gap in understanding the specific mechanisms through which central bank policies, green bond issuance, and credit availability directly impact green projects or influence short-term economic dynamics. Addressing this gap can guide policymakers in implementing timely interventions to foster green growth. Additionally, there is a need for a more comprehensive examination of the long-term sustainability of the identified economic benefits to ensure that positive trends remain robust and resilient over time. The investigation emphasizes critical components for predicting changes in green initiatives and vice versa. We recognize that consultations and policies supporting green financing initiatives can have a positive effect on the green economy by enhancing energy efficiency, fostering technological innovation, and strengthening financial infrastructure to achieve sustainability goals. Simplified policies aim to provide key insights into the performance of the studied variables, contributing to sustainable practices. Time series data, particularly ARDL tests for long-run relationships among variables, offer insights into environmental performance, demonstrating how central bank policies can catalyze changes in other variables and promote green growth. However, it is essential to note that this study primarily focuses on economic and environmental metrics, potentially overlooking future social impacts and considerations. Furthermore, the findings are predominantly centered on Pakistan, and their global relevance to different regions may vary. The investigation primarily concerns green finance and investments, without observing potential impacts on other sectors or industries. Additionally, the analysis of the time period from 1997 to 2022 may omit recent developments that could affect the current state of green investments. It is crucial to acknowledge that this research relies on available data, and limitations in data availability may affect the inclusivity of the analysis. Moreover, the study may not

extensively delve into the complexity of green bonds, missing detailed explorations of their features and implications. While econometric tests such as ARDL provide insights into short-run and long-run effects and the interactions between variables, it is essential not to rely solely on a fixed methodology like ARDL, excluding insights offered by other methods.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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